

The Use of Rewards to Stimulate Employee Creativity: The Mediating Moderation Role of Job Satisfaction and Creative Self-Efficacy

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ABSTRACT: This paper tested the moderated mediation model of intrinsic for creativity to explore the effects of intrinsic creativity on employee creativity. Using 320 supervisor-employee dyads of four educational institutes in Ghana. The results indicate that job satisfaction mediated the positive linkage between intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity. By integrating social cognitive theory and the interactionist perspective, we further recognized that creative self-efficacy could serve as a personal moderator in the linkage between job satisfaction and employee creativity. As the level of creative self-efficacy rose, the linkage between job satisfaction and employee creativity became stronger. The theoretical and practical implications of these results are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Creative Self-Efficacy; Employee Creativity; Intrinsic Rewards for Creativity; Job Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Creativity can be defined as the generation of novel, useful and constructive ideas (Amabile, 1988; Zhang et al., 2015), which is crucial for organizations to survive and experience growth in the current competitive world (Oldham & Cummings, 1996). Rewards play an essential role in determining and producing quality performance (Amabile, 1996). For instance, Eisenberger and Shanock, (2003) state that rewards are a critical factor in the work setting and stand to stimulate creativity between employees (Malik, Butt, & Choi, 2015). In addition, an individual factor also plays an important role in fostering employee creative behaviour (Shalley, Zhou, & Oldham, 2004). The current research used both approaches to present a comprehensive model to determine the creative behaviour of employees.

Regarding individuals' work behaviour Saks and Ashforth, (2000) found that employees do not always respond the same way to similar conditions, and thus to comprehend and predict their behaviour in workplace environments needs a research of both the individual and contextual factors. Byron and Khazanchi, (2012) indicate that the personal characteristic, can either strengthen or weaken the linkages between intrinsic rewards for creativity and the behaviour of employees (Yoon & Choi, 2010). More especially since the effectiveness of rewards for creativity on employee creativity depends on how individuals interpret rewards towards their behavioural disposition. The relationship between intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity depends on the nature of the workplace environment (Aletraris, 2010).

Nourishing employee creativity through particular rewards has been the emphasis of prior studies (Malik et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015) and intrinsic rewards for creativity has come out as a strong predictor of employee creativity (Yoon & Choi, 2010; Yoon, Sung, & Choi, 2015). For instance, intrinsic rewards stimulate and inspire a supportive work environment (Shalley, Zhou, & Oldham, 2004) and activate the essential contextual assets for employees to apply creative performance (Peterson & Luthans, 2006).

Previous research has also found that job satisfaction has a positive effect on employee creativity (Christen, Iyer, & Soberman, 2006; Hu & Zhao, 2016; Randhawa, 2004; Ziegler, Hagen, & Diehl, 2012). In their research, Christen et al. (2006) found a positive role of job satisfaction on employee creativity. Moreover, the job satisfaction posits that employees evaluate the availability of personal and contextual assets in their work content such as the degree to which he/she like or dislike their work, to achieve the given job (Hu & Zhao, 2016). Therefore, to increase creativity between employees, a manager can boost the employees' job satisfaction by strengthening the employees' evaluation of available assets via supporting and empowering them to succeed. Similarly, the concentration of intrinsic rewards for creativity is to increase the employees' sense of self-confidence and self-belief by declaring confidence in them, workplace high-level performance values, and motivating and encouraging them to perform creatively (Malik et al., 2015). Thus, employees working in a supportive environment are more inclined to be highly effective,

because in such an environment managers set clear goals, provide support, and empower their employees to reach greater heights (Afsar, Badir, & Saeed, 2014).

Together with contextual factors, understanding the employees' characteristics is paramount since it is an essential factor affecting creativity. Creative self-efficacy as a personal characteristic has been the topic of substantial engagement in a scientific research. Creative self-efficacy particularly refers to ones' ability to generate a novel and useful idea and concerns an inner, satisfying and supporting force that pushes employees to endure to produce creative results (Hu & Zhao, 2016). Creative self-efficacy further encourages employees to exercise their prowess by utilizing proper strategies in puzzling situations (Choi, 2004). In this research with creative self-efficacy as the moderator, we employ social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1982) as an overarching theory in the relationship between job satisfaction and employee creativity. Thus to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the boundary conditions when job satisfaction exerts a positive effect on employee creativity. One should consider individual moderators because there is no research, which has discovered the moderating roles of personal factors in the linkage between job satisfaction and employee creativity.

This paper explores the belief that intrinsic rewards for creativity can play an important role in increasing employees' job satisfaction and later influence fostering their creativity. Overall, the paper adds to the literature on intrinsic rewards for creativity by relating it with employee job satisfaction through creative self-efficacy and its following effect on fostering employee creativity in the Ghana context.

Figure 1. Research model.

THEORY AND HYPOTHESES

Employee Creativity

Creativity refers to the development of idea regarding products, practices, services, procedures, and processes that are judged to be fresh, novel, original and appropriate and constructive to solving problems (Oldham & Cummings, 1996; Ximenes et al., 2019). Creativity is an essential factor explore novel ideas that are appropriate and useful for organizational development and progress to create a competitive advantage (Zhou & George, 2001; Zacher & Johnson, 2015). Numerous studies (e.g., Chae, Seo, & Lee, 2013; Hu, Wang, Zhang, Bin, & Moriano, 2018; Joo, Yang, & Mclean, 2014; Pan, Sun, & Lam, 2020; Zhang, Zhang, Sun, Lytras, & De, 2018) presented that creativity is an essential factor for determining organizational competitive ability. The current research regarding employee creativity has mainly concentrated on identifying factors that support generating fresh ideas from employees, finally leading to innovation (Anderson, De Dreu, & Nijstad, 2004). More specifically, employee creativity considers as a critical part of employee solving problems, since employee creativity persuade finding constructive result to exiting problems and eventually leading to organizational transformation (Xi Zhang, Zhang, Sun, Lytras, & De, 2018). Based on Oldham and Cummings (1996) employee creativity affect by various contextual factors in the organization. Individuals and groups who establish an organization determine organizational creativity in organization.

Most previous studies regarding employee creativity have explored the impact of cognitive style and personality on individuals' creativity while others have examined the role of contextual factors, which form part of the work setting, on an employee's creativity (Shalley et al., 2004). Employees' creativity has been controlled by several job-related factors. The job

environment has a critical role in affecting employees' propensity to demonstrate innovative work behaviour at the organization (Ford & Gioia, 2000). In the current research, the focus is on personal and contextual factors such as intrinsic rewards for creativity, employee job satisfaction, and employee creative self-efficacy, which may have a considerable effect on employee creativity in organizations.

Intrinsic rewards and employee creativity

Intrinsic rewards for creativity are probably meant to enhance intrinsic motivation for a given job and is regarded as a positive indicator of creativity (Anderson, 2012; Baer, 2012; Dewett, 2007; Grant & Berry, 2011). Intrinsic rewards originate from work itself and demonstrate a sense of pleasure, attainment, endurance, and individual and professional development (Aletraris, 2010). Intrinsic rewards associated with intrinsic job motivation are useful for creativity (Yoon et al., 2015). Based on Vansteenkiste et al., (2006, p. 22) when employees receive intrinsic rewards they showed enhanced commitment to their job and they acquired a sense of direct fulfilment of the psychological basic needs. Therefore, intrinsic rewards could be regarded to have a strong effect on personal job motivation, which in turn determined the ability to work hard in the task (Aletraris, 2010). According to Vansteenkiste et al. (2006) and Yoon et al. (2015) receiving internal rewards stimulate, inspires and motivates employees to show more ability and work hard to perform creatively, since intrinsic rewards profoundly support task processing and perseverance.

Thus, we suggest that:

H₁. Intrinsic rewards for creativity related to employee creativity.

Role job satisfaction as a mediator

Job satisfaction refers to the positive feeling, which consequences of job experience and job considerations (Locke, 1976). According to Kim and Lee, (2011) when employees have an internal interest to showcase creativity, it reflects a high rank of job satisfaction. Previous studies have also reported that when employees are engaged in creative activities, the high rank of job satisfaction helps them to find solutions to various problems (Seibert, Grant, & Kraimer, 1999). Intrinsic rewards in tandem with intrinsic task motivation are helpful for employees to understand their job better, share their feelings easier, and further boost their job satisfaction (Linz & Semykina, 2012; Mark, 2016). Anggarwati and Eliyana, (2015) stated that internal incentive establishes a direct relationship between job satisfaction and employee creativity. Intrinsic rewards as an internal foster of job satisfaction stimulate employees through instilling confidence and inspiring the value of job-related results (Alice & Michael, 2009; Kim & Lee, 2011). Thus, we can suggest that job satisfaction mediate the relationship between intrinsic reward for creativity and employees' creativity and we propose the following hypothesis:

H₂. Job satisfaction mediates the effect of intrinsic rewards for creativity on employee creativity.

Creative self-efficacy as a moderator

Creative self-efficacy refers to the person's belief in their ability to perform novel and constructive ideas for an organization (Bandura, 1998). Tierney and Farmer, (2011) argue that when an individual has an inner confidence that he/she can perform a highly creative activity, it reveals a great rank of creative self-efficacy. Prior researchers have also indicated that when individuals are involved in creative tasks, a high level of self-efficacy helps them to find constructive results to a problem (Swati & Dhar, 2015). Evidence about job satisfaction and creative self-efficacy has revealed that an individual with high creative self-efficacy is more likely to be involved in the alternative task to perform a better effort as well as to make it easier and foster creative activities (Anggarwati & Eliyana, 2015; Hsieh, Hsieh, & Huang, 2016). Thus, given that creative self-efficacy is a personal moderator (Shalley et al., 2004) with a positive effect on employee creativity (Swati & Dhar, 2015; Tierney & Farmer, 2002), by integrating social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1982) as our overarching theory, we suggest that creative self-efficacy is an essential individual factor that moderates the linkage between employee job satisfaction and employee creativity.

Based on social cognitive theory, apparent employee job satisfaction may affect three bases of creative self-efficacy: Firstly, employee job satisfaction impart a 'can do' confidence in employees (Dave et al., 2011; Luzipo & Dyk, 2018), this confidence performs as an effective social encouragement determining their efficacy confidence (Diseth, Danielsen, & Samdal, 2012; Zhang et al., 2015). Secondly, given the employee job satisfaction impart, employees will increasingly accrue a history of fruitful experiences in consultation and exceeding (Andrews, 2005; Klaijnsen, Vermeulen, & Martens, 2018). Such enactive achievements created on mastery experiences produce the most important asset of self-efficacy evidence (Bandura, 1986). Finally, an apparent employee job satisfaction may help as the solid social-emotional support, drive positive employee evaluations of their creative abilities and support

them to overcome physiological stimulation when acting challenging and new tasks, thus inspiring their creative self- efficacy (Hsieh et al., 2016; Jiang & Gu, 2017).

More specifically, a recent study recognized that creative self-efficacy increases employee creativity (Anggarwati & Eliyana, 2015). Employees who have high creative self-efficacy will be more to mobilize their creative potentials into creating a novel idea, which in turn lead their creative product in an organization (Styliani, 2015; Swati & Dhar, 2015; Tang & Chang, 2010). Creative self-efficacy enhances employees' independence in decision-making which affects job-related results (Tierney & Farmer, 2002) and further provides employees with a significant chance for autonomy and independence in how to do the work. Thus, employees in the workplace with high creative self-efficacy would be content and be more independent and confident to respond to job satisfaction. Particularly, employees with greater creative self-efficacy are more satisfied and have an opportunity to discover suitable and creative mixtures of work techniques (Chen & Zhang, 2018), to escape from routinized work and discover the new and best result to a problem (Jiang & Gu, 2017), hence supporting the dispositional source of creative self-efficacy development is paramount (Tierney & Farmer, 2011). Thus, we suggest that:

H₃. Creative self-efficacy moderates the effect of employee job satisfaction on employee creativity such that relationships are strengthened when creative self-efficacy is high rather than low.

METHOD

Sample and procedure

Employees and their immediate supervisors registered in executive training programs from four public institutes in Accra capital of Ghana participated in the current research. To evade possible common method variance, the data was collected from multiple sources. In particular, employees evaluate independent variables (intrinsic reward for creativity), mediating variable (job satisfaction) and the moderating variable (creative self-efficacy). On a distinct evaluation procedure, their immediate supervisors evaluated the outcome variable (employee creativity). One researcher and associates visited the entire participants (employees and their immediate supervisors) to explain the research objective and the survey implementing procedures. Respondents participated voluntarily and the researcher strictly guaranteed that their identities would not be disclosed. To match employees' evaluation with their immediate supervisors' evaluation and further recognize work teams participating employees the researcher and his associates first coded all surveys and then given surveys and return envelopes to respondents. All participants were instructed to envelop the completed surveys and returned them directly to the researcher and his associates. In the current research before distributing the survey, the survey scales were translated from English to Persian based translation/back-translation procedure (Brislin, 1980). Survey questionnaires were distributed among 350 employees and their immediate supervisors from 4 Accra public institutes in Ghana. We excluded 30 uncompleted questionnaires only from self-questionnaire data, the final data included 320 matching subordinates and their immediate supervisors (final response rate = 80%).

The final analysis data included surveys from four public Accra institutes (48% Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, 15% Ghana Communication Technology University, 22% Tarkwa University of Science and Technology, 15% Regent University of Science and Technology). From the employee data, 60.3% were male, and 37.5% were between 30-40 years of age. Their work experience were mostly more than six years (26.3%). In education, 56.6% had a bachelor, 25.6% had a master's degree, meanwhile, 17.8% had a PhD degree.

Control Variables

Previous researchers have recognized the positive effects of different demographic variables such as age, gender, educational level, and work experience on employee creativity (Amabile, 1988; Zhang & Bartol, 2010), thus in the current research age, gender, educational level, and work experience were controlled variables.

Measures

Intrinsic rewards for creativity was measured using Baer, Oldham, and Cummings, (2003) Seven-item scale ($\alpha = .79$). To measure job satisfaction, we used a five-item scale ($\alpha = .80$) developed by Hackman and Oldham, (1975). To measure creative self-efficacy, we used a five-item scale ($\alpha = .93$) developed by Schwarzer et al., (1999) and modified by Malik et al., (2015). Finally, we measured employee creativity using a nine-item scale ($\alpha = .83$) developed by Zhou and George, (2001). Each item in this research was rated on a five-point Likert-type scale "1 = strongly disagree" to "5 = strongly agree".

RESULTS

Measurement model

Table 3 shows the means, standard deviations, correlations, and reliabilities between all research variables.

Before testing hypotheses, to establish the convergent and discriminant validity of the current research variables (intrinsic reward for creativity, job satisfaction, creative self-efficacy, and employee creativity), we conducted confirmatory factor analysis using Amos 23. As displayed in

Table 1, the outcomes of our model comparisons demonstrated that our baseline model, which comprises four-factor, provided a great fit to the data ($\chi^2(243) = 418.262, p < 0.001, RMSEA = 0.05, IFI = 0.94, TLI = 0.93$ and $CFI = 0.94$). Furthermore, the chi-square difference test and multiple indexes (CFI, TLI, and RMSEA) generally showed that the baseline model provided a great fit to the data compared to any of the alternative three-factor, two-factor and one-factor models (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988).

Through the reliability and validity analyses of the measures, we examined the measurement model. The results illustrated in Table 2. The reliability of the individual item was examined by testing each measure factor loadings on its corresponding construct. As the results demonstrate, the reliability of the individual item was generally strong for the constructs. In addition, Table 2 displays that Cronbach’s α reached from .79 to .93, which are greater than the standard value of .70, demonstrating the reliability of all measures.

To check the convergent validity we assessed the average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) of the constructs. The AVE values reached from .52 to .58 and are greater than the standard value of .50. The scores of CR reached from .97 to .98, which are greater than the standard value of .70. Thus, a satisfactory convergent validity was provided for the measurement model.

Discriminant validity was assessed by comparing the squared correlation between constructs with the AVE of the individual construct (Barclay, Higgins, & Thompson, 1995). Fornell and Larcker, (1981) suggested, “the square of the correlation between two constructs should be less than their corresponding average variance extracted (AVE)”. The analysis showed the squared correlation between constructs were lower than the AVE of the individual construct, which confirmed the discriminant validity Table 2.

Common method bias

We conducted Harman’s single-factor analysis based on the procedure suggested by Podsakoff et al., (2003). We entered all items in an exploratory factor analysis, where the first factor was found to account for only 25% of the total variance, and in which both eigenvalue and screen plot analysis strongly recommended multiple factors. This recommended that common method bias was not problematic.

Table 1. Comparison of measurement models.

Models	Factors	χ^2	$\Delta\chi^2$	d.f.	IFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
1	Baseline four-factor model	418.262***		243	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.05
2	Three-factor model: creative self-efficacy and job satisfaction, intrinsic reward for creativity and employee creativity were combined into one factor	830.988***	412.726***	246	0.82	0.79	0.82	0.09
3	Two- factor model: intrinsic reward for creativity, creative self-efficacy and job satisfaction were combined with employee creativity into one factor	1527.023***	696.035***	248	0.60	0.55	0.60	0.12
4	One- factor model: intrinsic reward for creativity and creative self-efficacy; job satisfaction and employee creativity were combined into one factor	1881.833***	354.81***	249	0.49	0.43	0.49	0.14

*** $p < .001$.

Table 2. Findings on the measurement model

Constructs	Item	Loadings	α	KMO	AVE	CR
IR	IR1	0.891				
	IR2	0.789				
	IR3	0.874				
	IR4	0.791				
	IR5	0.982				
	IR6	0.878				
	IR7	0.787	0.79	0.867	0.54	0.98
JS	JS1	0.861				
	JS2	0.756				
	JS3	0.892				
	JS4	0.861				
	JS5	0.798	0.80	0.904	0.58	0.98
CSE	CSE1	0.761				
	CSE2	0.764				
	CSE3	0.818				
	CSE4	0.761				
	CSE5	0.887	0.93	0.804	0.53	0.97
ECR	ECR1	0.887				
	ECR2	0.903				
	ECR3	0.813				
	ECR4	0.987				
	ECR5	0.842				
	ECR6	0.904				
	ECR7	0.871				
	ECR8	0.832				
	ECR9	0.943	0.83	0.875	0.52	0.98

Table 3. Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations between research Variables.

Variables	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Gender	1.60	0.49	-							
2. Age	2.33	0.99	.14*	-						
3. Work Experience	3.06	1.83	.08	.84**	-					
4. Educational Level	2.01	1.23	.10*	.44**	.36**	-				
5. Intrinsic Reward for Creativity	4.41	0.50	.04	-.05	.01	.05	(.77)			
6. Job Satisfaction	3.83	0.67	-.15	-.39	.05	-.10	.30**	(.78)		
7. Creative Self-efficacy	3.89	0.79	-.09	.08	.11*	-.03	.14*	.32**	(.83)	
8. Employee Creativity	4.06	0.48	.01	.05	.02	-.01	.33**	.53**	.30**	(.84)

Note: *N* = 320. AVEs are displayed in parentheses on the diagonal.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

Table 4. Results of hierarchical regression analysis.

Independent	Job Satisfaction		Employee Creativity				
	Model1	Model2	Model3	Model3	Model4	Model5	Model6
Control Variable							
Gender	-.18	-.20	-.00	-.02	.05	.04	.02
Age Group	-.13	-.07	.06	.10	.13*	.13*	.09
Work Experience	.09	.07	-.02	-.04	-.06	-.06	-.04
Educational Level	-.05	-.07	-.01	-.02	.00	-.01	-.00
Main Effects							
Intrinsic Reward for Creativity		.42***		.33***	.18***	.17***	.22***
Mediator Effects							
Job Satisfaction					.35***	.27***	.23***
Moderator Effects							
Creative self-efficacy						.27***	.23***
Interaction Effects							
Intrinsic Reward for Creativity × Creative self-efficacy							.06***
Overall <i>F</i>	3.95**	10.33***	0.38	8.69**	26.37***	28.41***	32.34***
<i>R</i> ²	.04	.14***	.00	.12***	.34***	.39***	.45***
Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	.13	.13***	-.00	.11***	.32***	.37***	.44***
Change <i>R</i> ²	.05	.09***	.00	.12***	.21***	.05***	.06***

Hypothesis testing

To test the hypotheses, a series of multiple regression analyses were conducted by including control variables and the main variables of the paper in several stages. To test Hypothesis 1 and 2 the variables were included in the model in three stages. First, the control variables of gender, age, work experience, and educational level were included, following by the independent variable of intrinsic rewards for creativity, and finally, the mediator (job satisfaction) was included to test the mediation effect. As demonstrated in Table 4, intrinsic rewards for creativity positively associated with employee creativity ($\beta = .33, p < .001$), thus supported Hypotheses 1.

Regarding the testing of the hypotheses 2 mediation procedure recommended by Baron, and Kenny, (1986) was followed. The intrinsic reward for creativity was positively related to job satisfaction ($\beta = .42, p < .001$). Furthermore, when job satisfaction was included, the linkage between intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity became weaker but significant ($\beta = .18, p < .001$), whereas job satisfaction, was found to be positively associated with employee creativity ($\beta = .35, p < .001$), thus, Hypothesis 2 was partially supported.

Hypothesis 3 predicted the moderating roles of creative self-efficacy in the linkage between employee job satisfaction and employee creativity. We included employee job satisfaction, creative self-efficacy to evade multicollinearity with their product terms in the regressions of moderation (Aiken & West, 1991). The employee job satisfaction × creative self-efficacy interaction term significant for employee creativity ($\beta = .06, p < .001$) supported Hypothesis 3. **Error! Reference source not found.** displayed the nature of the interaction that was acquired via plotting values plus and minus one standard deviation from the means of employee job satisfaction and creative self-efficacy. As expected, when creative self-efficacy is low, employee job satisfaction has less impact on employee creativity and when creative self-efficacy is high, the linkage between employee job satisfaction and employee creativity is strengthened.

Figure 2. Creative-self efficacy as a moderator for the relationship between employee job satisfaction and employee creativity.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this research was to explore the moderated mediation model placing on intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity. Our empirical findings reveal that job satisfaction drives as a mediating mechanism relation intrinsic rewards for creativity to employee creativity. Moreover, through employing social cognitive theory as an overarching theory creative self-efficacy functions as boundary conditions that moderate the linkage between employee job satisfaction and employee creativity. The results have significant implications for how researchers and seniors’ executives perceive the benefits of the use of intrinsic rewards for creativity.

Theoretical implications

Our results support the notion of understanding more about the drivers of creativity between individuals through a focus on inspiring employees and the interest they have in intrinsic rewards in the workplace. Intrinsic rewards encourage employees and in addition foster their ability to generate novel and constructive ideas. Intrinsic rewards satisfy and as well as give them freedom and autonomy by centering emphasis on the importance and value of job roles. They inspire the intellectual abilities of employees and stimulate them to create occasions to influence their job roles, which leads to higher ranks of creativity. Our findings also emphasize the need to consider studying both individual and contextual factors in addition to their interaction in a simple intrinsic rewards-support-creativity model to understand in ways that are more complex about how and under what conditions intrinsic rewards might support creativity.

Second, our findings more clearly explain how intrinsic rewards as a contextual factor support employee creativity by targeting the significant mediating role of job satisfaction personal factors. Previous studies concentrated mainly on the commitment to creativity as a mediator by which intrinsic rewards affect employee creativity. In the current research, however, we established that job satisfaction performs as the mediating mechanism relating intrinsic rewards with employee creativity. These outcomes recommend that one important mechanism through which intrinsic rewards can influence employee creativity is creating a

workplace as an environment where employees feel positive and internal content while performing creativity. The results showed here consequently add significant empirical evidence to help assertion that, below the accurate conditions (e.g. high level of creative self-efficacy), intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity can be an important supporter of job satisfaction and in turn boost employees' creativity (Kim & Lee, 2011).

Finally, our finding revealed that social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1982) could be employed as an overarching theory to illuminate the mechanism and boundary conditions of how and when intrinsic rewards for creativity can affect employee creativity. As opposed to the prior researches, which also used social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1982) as a principal theoretical clarification of the linkage between extrinsic rewards and creative performance (Zhang et al., 2015). As a result, our research adds to the existing literature by expanding a new theoretical perspective for investigating the link of intrinsic reward for creativity to employee creativity.

Practical implications

Numerous practical implications can be derived from this research. Managers must know what encourages creativity between employees in the workplace environment. First, it recommends that providing intrinsic rewards for shaping a harmonious environment in the workplace is effective in producing internal interest or enthusiasm of employees, which in turn arias their job satisfaction. Managers should create a good workplace environment; such an environment inspires employees and further enhances their internal interest and creative capability to perform creativity. In a good environment, employees feel positive, which in turn foster their creative behaviour by increasing the internal interest and creative capability (Kim & Lee, 2011). Second, managers should provide an environment that encourages job satisfaction (Seibert et al., 1999). Thus, managers should also ensure that intrinsic rewards are helpful for employees to comprehend better their job, ease shares their feelings, and further boost their job satisfaction. Employees must recognize the expectations of managers and have confident of achieving those (Alice & Michael, 2009). For instance, the degree of freedom is a key consideration in job strategy. Our results recommend that managers should have employees define their approaches, hop, and exertion to achieve the tasks by rewarding them intrinsically. Employees also need to be specified the autonomy and time to experiment with constructive results to solving problem thus they could shape a sense of confidence in their capability to achieve creative tasks. Because the sense of confidence increases, internal work interest, and employees with more internal work interest has a high rank of job satisfaction.

Third, it is also essential for managers to offer a sense of meaningfulness and effectiveness to employees' effort, offer-growing response about the task accomplished, and provide chances for individual development and growth, which can be led to make employees become more job satisfied and self-efficacy and use high creative exertion to their works. Employees whit high creative self-efficacy are more probable to involve in an alternative task to perform a better effort as well as to make it easier and foster creative activities (Anggarwati & Eliyana, 2015). Moreover, employees with self-efficacy in the works might arise with novel and practical thoughts, which may shape the source for organizational creativities that lead to better competitive advantage (Jiang & Gu, 2017).

Limitations

Regardless of these contributions, numerous limitations need to be distinguished. First, in the current research, the sample contained only 320 subordinate and their immediate supervisor dyads; therefore, the hypotheses must be examined another time by researching with a broader, more general sample. Second, though we measure individual demographic characteristics (e.g. age, gender, level of education and work experience) as control variables, other factor linked to employee creativity (hierarchical level length) must likewise be preserved as control variables in further study (Joo et al., 2014). Third, the results that job satisfaction mediated the linkage between intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity to some level. Nevertheless, since the results revealed that the coefficient decreased, there might be additional mediator variables included in this linkage. In further researches, more variables can be presented in the model to research the linkage between intrinsic rewards for creativity and employee creativity. Fourth, the sample was collected from four higher education institutes in a single geographic area. This may have shaped results that are specific contextually and culturally, thus limiting the researches generalizability. Future studies can consider using a sample from different organizations and geographic areas. Nevertheless, collecting a sample from different organizations and geographic area may enhance the generalizability of the study.

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